

Normal coordinate analysis: The assigned frequencies for these fundamentals and the structural parameters used in the present investigation are presented in Table 1. A normal coordinate analysis⁴⁻⁶ has been carried out and a set of molecular constants have been reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—KINETIC CONSTANTS (10^{-36} kg), VALENCE FORCE CONSTANTS (10^2 N m⁻¹) AND MEAN SQUARE AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION (10^{-3} Å²) OF SF₄ MOLECULE AT 298.16 K

	Kinetic constants <i>k</i>	Force constants <i>f</i>	Mean square amplitudes <i>σ</i>
<i>d</i>	4.112 83	5.582 32	2.546 45
<i>dd</i>	1.775 37	1.845 62	0.351 88
<i>D</i>	2.544 86	3.175 99	1.670 99
<i>DD</i>	0.649 19	-1.129 41	-0.633 44
<i>Dd</i>	0.119 97	0.151 34	0.077 10
<i>Dα</i>	-0.203 62	-0.163 00	0.015 23
<i>Dβ</i>	0.112 97	0.020 85	-0.031 45
<i>dα</i>	1.941 64	-1.554 49	0.621 14
<i>dβ</i>	1.196 09	0.220 79	-0.237 90
<i>α</i>	2.426 15	1.942 25	1.389 03
<i>αβ</i>	-1.002 05	-0.184 82	0.240 53
<i>β</i>	1.642 89	0.682 99	1.425 08
<i>ββ</i>	0.500 88	-0.034 27	0.119 31

Non-bonded mean amplitudes at 298.16 K (10^{-3} Å):
($F_1 - F_2$) = 8.061 82; ($F_3 - F_4$) = 6.697 83.

From Table 2, it is observed that the bond angle interaction kinetic constants $k_{Dα}$ and $k_{αα}$ and the angle-angle interaction constant $k_{αβ}$ are negative as expected. It is interesting to note that the corresponding force constants are also negative. The sign of force constant is a measure of localisation or delocalisation in a molecule⁷. Further, it is seen that $f_α$ is higher than f_D which suggests that the S-F_α bond is stronger than S-F₁ bond. The force constants evaluated are in the expected range.

The vibrational mean square amplitudes corresponding to the bonded lengths and the mean amplitudes corresponding to non-bonded lengths are evaluated in the present study and the values obtained in the expected range confirms the correctness of the assignment. The vibrational mean amplitude values are useful in the interpretation of electron diffraction data.

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Mode of Solidification and Flexural Strength of Naphthalene-Benzil System

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THE directional solidification is an important method for strengthening behaviour of eutectic alloys. The structural morphology and mechanical behaviour of directionally grown non-faceted-non-faceted binary eutectics were recently investigated^{1,2}. Significant work has been done on the morphological studies of directionally grown faceted-faceted samples³. Some investigations have been carried out on solidification and strength properties of faceted-non-faceted and non-faceted-non-faceted systems^{4,5}.

Investigations on flexural strengths of unidirectionally and randomly grown samples of naphthalene, benzil and their eutectic are presented in this paper. The results are interpreted on the basis of morphologies of these systems.

Experimental

Naphthalene (L.R., Reidel) was purified by slow sublimation followed by repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate and benzil (L.R., Loba) was purified by repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate. Eutectic (with eutectic temperature 51°) was prepared by accurately weighing the two components in the eutectic ratio (42 mole% of benzil)⁶. The unidirectional growth of naphthalene, benzil and their eutectic were carried out by the method described earlier⁷.

The single point loading method was used for the determination of flexural strength. The apparatus consisted of two knife edges (5.2 cm apart) and an arrangement for applying the load at the centre. The flexural strength has been calculated by the equation,

$$\sigma_f = \frac{8PL}{\pi d^3}$$

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TABLE 1—FLEXURAL STRENGTHS OF NAPHTHALENE, BENZIL AND NAPHTHALENE—BENZIL EUTECTIC

Mode of solidification	Rate of solidification $\times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Diameter cm	Load kg	Flexural strength kg cm^{-2}	Mean flexural strength* kg cm^{-2}
<i>Naphthalene</i>					
Random	—	1.125	1.55	14.41	14.35
Unidirectional	54.25	1.142	1.75	15.51	
	34.37	1.173	1.90	15.58	
	25.28	1.035	1.55	18.50	
	15.94	1.195	3.30	25.60	
	12.33	1.182	2.95	23.64	
	10.47	1.192	1.95	15.24	
<i>Benzil</i>					
Random	—	1.49	1.40	5.60	5.90
Unidirectional	38.7	1.47	1.20	5.00	4.75
	22.4	1.42	0.94	4.35	4.25
	15.6	1.42	0.90	4.16	4.18
<i>Naphthalene—benzil eutectic</i>					
Random	—	1.40	6.80	32.80	33.17
Unidirectional	15.90	1.35	8.30	44.65	45.73
	10.92	1.40	7.60	36.66	35.82
	4.46	1.42	9.30	42.49	41.42

*Values are the mean values as obtained in Ref. 8.

where, σ_F is the flexural strength in kg cm^{-2} , P is the maximum load, L is the span length in cm and d is the diameter in cm of the sample.

Results and Discussion

The values of flexural strengths of randomly and unidirectionally grown samples of naphthalene, benzil and their eutectic are provided in Table 1, which also contains the values of mean flexural strength.

The flexural strengths of naphthalene were determined at different rates of solidification in order to study the effect of solidification rates on flexural strengths. Lower flexural strength values (15.51 kg cm^{-2}) were observed at a fast rate of solidification of $54.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Understandably, the values at fast rates of solidification are quite near the values from randomly grown samples. At the moderate rate of solidification of $15.94 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, the maximum in the flexural strength with a value of 25.6 kg cm^{-2} was observed, which is 56.5% more than the flexural strength of its randomly grown samples, *i.e.* 14.35 kg cm^{-2} . The value again decreased to 15.24 kg cm^{-2} at a much slower rate of $10.47 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$.

The lower flexural strength at randomly solidified samples of naphthalene is attributed to the formation of imperfection in the form of cracks and voids. In such cases, the nucleation begins at a large number of sites giving rise to imperfections at the grain boundary.

Directional solidification on naphthalene brings about parallelism of fibers in the growth direction

resulting in higher values of flexural strengths. The rise and fall in the values of flexural strengths of naphthalene is attributed to structural changes taking place with the variation in growth rates. The near perfect alignment in fibers occurs at a certain growth rate to give the maximum value to flexural strength. In case of benzil (Table 1), the mean flexural strength of unidirectionally grown sample at $38.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ is 4.75 kg cm^{-2} , which is slightly lower than the value 5.9 kg cm^{-2} of randomly grown sample. This is due to the formation of cracks perpendicular to the growth direction of the sample. The flexural strengths of benzil decrease as the rate of solidification decreases. The flexural strengths of naphthalene—benzil eutectic were found to be of the order of 33.17 and 45.73 kg cm^{-2} for randomly and unidirectionally grown eutectic samples, respectively, which are much higher than similar values of single components.

The strength properties of the eutectic are governed by its structural morphology. Unidirectional solidification brings about coupled growth to give a composite microstructure with fibers aligned parallel to the growth direction and thus account for the greater strength in unidirectionally solidified eutectic samples. In eutectic, another important factor to give increased strength is the thermodynamic stability due to equilibrium of the two components.

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studies prompted us to synthesise some new compounds (1) as possible antineoplastic agents in which the pyrazole moiety is linked at one side of azo linkage and benzothiazole to the other side, so as to increase the overall activity of the azo group.

1

Synthesis of some New Benzothiazolylazopyrazoles

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BIOLOGICAL importance of azo compounds is well known for their use as antineoplastics¹, antidiabetics², antiseptics^{3,4} and other useful chemotherapeutics⁵, e.g. *N,N*-bis (2-chlorophenyl)-*p*-phenylazoaniline has been found to possess tumor inhibitory activity⁶. Moreover, pyrazoles and benzothiazoles are also considered as potent biologically active compounds⁷⁻¹⁴. It has been found that the activity of azo linkage increases on the incorporation of suitable heterocyclic nuclei. These

The compounds reported herein have been synthesised by reacting various 2-benzothiazolylhydrazono-1-(*N*-aminophenyl)-1,3-butanedione, 3-benzothiazolylhydrazonopentane-2,4-dione, 2-benzothiazolylhydrazono-1-[*N*-amino(2-chlorophenyl)]-butane-1,3-dione with thiosemicarbazide. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, and ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, uv-vis spectra on a Carl-Zeiss specord spectrophotometer, umr spectra (CDCl₃ + TFA) using TMS as internal standard on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument, and mass spectra

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-4-BENZOTHAZOLYL-AZO-*N*-THIOCARBAMOYL PYRAZOLES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	M.p	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
1.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	238	50	Orange	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
2.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	176	55	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
3.	5-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	242	55	Orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
4.	6-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	250	50	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
5.	6-Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	264	45	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₆ S ₂ Cl
6.	6-Br	CH ₃	CH ₃	250	50	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₆ S ₂ Br
7.	6-NO ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	166	60	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
8.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	110	50	Orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
9.	5-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	226	55	Red	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
10.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	120	45	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
11.	H	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	220	55	Orange	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₇ S ₂
12.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	150	60	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
13.	5-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	210	60	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
14.	6-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	230	55	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
15.	6-Cl	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	194	50	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ S ₂ Cl
16.	6-Br	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	184	55	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ S ₂ Br
17.	6-NO ₂	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	200	60	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂
18.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	190	45	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
19.	5-OCH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	130	50	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
20.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	250	45	Red	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
21.	5-NO ₂ -6-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	161	60	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂
22.	H	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₄ Cl	166	50	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₂ Cl
23.	H	C=O	C=O	236	40	Orange	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂

*All compounds gave consistent N and S analysis.